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A Conversation Analysis of Recorded Hausa Interactions

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ABSTRACT

With the growing incapacity of the syntactic method of analysis to capture and explicate the puzzling relationship between language forms and the meanings they are used to convey, the study of language in actual use has become an area deserving attention of researchers in language studies (MacCarthy, N. 1991). Recent studies into the nature of language in actual use have revealed that there are a number of influencing factors surrounding the use of language to mean. It is particularly observed that the relationship between linguistic forms and communicative function is in most part an area of pragmatics that forms the core of the field of Discourse Analysis (See: Mary, J.L. 1993; MacCarthy, N. 2001, Paltridge, B. 2007, etc.). This paper explored the underlying rules of how language works in conversation interaction amongst Hausa speakers. The study made use of the conventional tools of Conversation Analysis (CA) to analyze, in particular, how argument conversations are initiated, structured and managed within the framework of an informal social setting among participants in talks. The insight gained from the analysis revealed among other things, that arguments in casual conversation are not pre-arranged but occur in the course of normal transactions with topics emerging abruptly, either initiated by a statement or by asking question.

Keywords: linguistic forms: communicative function: conversation analysis: argument conversation

INTRODUCTION

By way of method, conversation Analysis, CA is a technical system of exploration of the underlying rules of how language works in a given social setting. It takes the most decisive departure from Chomsky's (1957) view that "linguistic performance" is of little relevance to the linguists. The CA's object of study is talk-in-interaction that provides an extraordinary rich evidence of how language is used to perform social activities (Litosselite 2010). CA considers that ordinary conversation construct social realities (Sacks, H. 1995; 2004). To illustrate these facts therefore, the CA analysts use audio or video recording and render them into the transcripts in order to examine how our talks organize the world within specific social settings. In this paper, I would first introduce the reader to how talks in interactions are traditionally collected as sample data, transcribed, and analyzed within the CA enterprise for a better understanding of how our investigation works.

First and foremost, the central feature common to spoken discourse analysis is „natural purity“. Lyons, (1981) describes discourse data as one that must be free from all elements of regularization, standardization and decontextualization which have been the characteristic features of intuitive data often constructed and used by gramarians. Like ethnomethodology (Girfinkel, H. 1967), the CA does not emphasize on building structural models but strictly on the close observation of the behaviors of participants in talks and on patterns which recur over a wide range of natural data (McCarthy, N. 1991). This means that the analysis of conversation is typically based on linguistic output of someone other than the analyst. Such material is what Brown, G. and Yule (1983) described as „performance data“. Such data due to its natural purity may

contain features like hesitation, pauses, slips of the tongue, and sometimes non-standard forms. Thus, heavy emphasis is put on the data and patterns recurrently displayed thereon without any distortion from the hands of the analyst. The emphasis on purity and non-standardization therefore dictates strictly on the data's method of collection.

In the process of recording strict maintenance of natural atmosphere is therefore paramount. Participants in conversation should not be pre-informed of their talks being recorded, otherwise they would directly skip from their natural disposition of the talks to constructing certain artificial conducts of the talks, like the preparedness of someone placed before an interviewer or a camera. To conform to the ethics of recording talks however, participants in interaction should and ought to be notified after the recording is completed and then, their consent is solicited. Where the said participants appear unwilling to give their consent the recorder of the talks should destroy the recordings made before the participants' own eyes.

Next to the recording stage is the important but tedious task of transcribing talks. The venture can be described as a way of rendering sounds or speech on paper in a conventional fashion. Often transcripts are not seen as the direct replica of the data of CA, but as according to Have, H ten (1990, 2007), a rather conventional way to capture and present the phenomena of interest in written form. Anderson, S.R. (1993) too has noted that transcriptions should not be taken as substitutes for the recordings but as a selected theory laden rendering of certain aspects of what the tape has preserved of the original interaction. Heath, C. and Luff, P. (1993) describes the process of transcription in CA as analytical tools that provides the researcher with understanding and insight into the participants conduct including the way of noticing, even discovering particular events helping them focus analytic attention into the participants' socio-cultural organization.

Language is not merely a means of communication but also a medium through which social realities are negotiated, identities constructed, and relationships maintained. Conversation as a form of spoken discourse serves as a rich site for analyzing language use in its most natural and interactive form. However, while Hausa is still one of the most widely spoken languages in West Africa (Newman, P. 2000), scholarly attention to the structural and pragmatic features of the language conversational discourse remains limited especially from a discourse analytical perspective. Existing studies in Hausa linguistics have largely focused on grammar and lexicon often overlooking the semiotic and discursive nature of everyday conversation. It is against this background that this research work is motivated replenishing the need to bridge the gap by examining Hausa conversation using the tools of discourse analysis to discover how cultural norms shape discursive practices.

This study therefore seeks to analyze selected recorded Hausa informal conversations in order to uncover the discourse feature embedded in them, such as the patterns of interaction and how they reflect socio-cultural and communicative norms of Hausa speakers. Addressing this problem will contribute to both discourse analysis and African language studies by offering insights into the linguistic and pragmatic dimensions and nuances of Hausa oral interaction.

METHOD

Speech act theory forms the basic framework for qualitative presumption. Language is used to do things. It is viewed as something more than merely a formal system of sound and meaning correspondence, something far from being just stretches of sentences to which meanings are assigned but a means by which users construct „Speech Acts“, Austin, J.L. (1962). There is nowhere in the view of the researcher to witness how speech acts work as in the medium of conversation. Speech acts are never apparent or immediately evident in a formal framework where language is viewed as all and only the correct sentences are supposed to be derived by a grammar. The reason to this claim is that there is no such thing as a correct conversation in the sense that generative grammarians define a correct sentence. Conversation is what actually occurs among people. It is when people use language interactively that their speech acting makes sense in their own common context of use which involves the overall background knowledge of participants: cultural interpersonal etc, that helps in achieving the social goals that their conversational interaction is set to achieve. Austin, J.L. (1962) describes conversation from two points of view; first from the point of view of „content“ which involves what the conversation is about, the topic discussed and how they are brought into conversation. Second, from the point of view of whether or not the topic discussed are overtly

announced presupposed or even hidden in other ways. In the same way, this view also ventures to look at the mechanisms for organizing conversations. For instance, it looks at how topics are opened and closed, managed among participants, how moves are organized and structured as well as how the traffic flows of conversation are ran and managed (see Sacks H. 1995; Paltridge B. 2007).

Against the background just explained, the researcher adopted qualitative descriptive design anchored in discourse analysis to conduct the research. This approach allows for a detailed interpretive examination of natural use of language within real conversational atmosphere among Hausa speakers.

The population of the study comprised native Hausa speakers of Sakkwatanci dialect who were engaged in informal conversational interactions in various contexts such as politics, family discussions, peer interactions and community dialogues of some sorts where participants in talks exercised equal rights in the conduct of talks. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select six to eight audio-recorded conversations each ranging between 5 to 10 minutes. In a typical Hausa community, people are of the habit of sitting at leisure times, in patches of small group of about the size of between 5 to 10 persons called „dabas“. Dabas are places where people sit to discuss issues of the time in leisure free and friendly atmosphere. The group comprises individuals of nearly the same age group. People constituting a Daba are often individuals of the same social status or to say the least those who considered themselves friends of equal rights. Talks that hold in such a setting are always free and informal with none of the participants having the right or authority to infringe their right on others, nor censor one another on their equal rights to the talks. It is thus, an informal gathering and the kinds of talks conducted are purely free, informal and natural.

The primary data was collected through audio recording of spontaneous conversations among Hausa speakers. In the process of recordings, strict maintenance of natural atmosphere was ensured. Participants in the recorded conversations were not pre-informed of their talks being recorded. But, in order to conform to the ethics of recording talks the participants were fully notified after the recording was completed and their consent was fully solicited.

Usually, in CA, the data is a sample collection of recorded talks as actually produced by participants in conversation. Therefore, the instrument used in its collection were talks recording facilities and in this work such facilities were tapes and audio recorders, that were believed to be capable of capturing conversation at the instance it is taking place. The method of data analysis employed was the improved version of one developed by Sindair, J. and Coulthard, R.M. (1975). It is known for its relative simplicity and powerful instruments that bear direct connections with the study of speech acts. Its systematic handling of data makes it capable of capturing the conversations larger structure. Moreso discourse analysts have found the model's effectiveness for application in the analysis of non- formal forms of conversation. That, although informal conversations take place under free atmosphere, they are believed to exhibit some degree of structuredness (MacCarthy, N. 1991:19).

The data analysis focused on two major points of view: content and form. The content view investigated what topics of conversation were about; how they were brought about and how they were managed. The formal view on the other hand discerned how the conversation worked. What rule were observed and how sequencing were achieved.

The transcription of the data was also the analysis in its actual sense. To achieve this, the researcher employed a number of conventions (i.e. Systems and devices). Such conventions are the ones commonly used in CA worldwide. They are used to capture the natural aspects of conversations, such as might include non-linguistic features like gestures laughter, pauses, background noise etc. such natural aspects are considered invaluable in helping to identify the ways in which people in conversation were able to establish the traffic rules of conversation (i.e. conversation flow) using linguistic means. At the bottom end of our transcribed data, a set of conversational symbols used and what they stand for was given to serve as a guide and key to reading the transcriptions. A detail commentary of the analysis was made to follow afterwards.

Although, the problem of translating transcripts is hardly a methodological issue in CA, it is nonetheless a useful tool for presenting the data analysis to those readers who are not familiar with the language under study (i.e. Hausa). For this work, the researcher chose to present the material in the original language with a translation into the language of publication (i.e. English) immediately below it line by line. However, in this paper, translation is restricted to that portion of the data involved in analytical discussion.

Finally, in this work although, gender and age were considered to constitute important aspect of the study the researcher chose to limit the focus of the study to male participants of age range between 18 and 50 years for convenience. This choice was due to two compelling reasons. First because females participants are not easy to access for cultural restrictions. Second because it is hardly likely for participants in casual conversation to be of the same age group and people of between 18 and 50 can be believed to be linguistically mature and fairly well-informed about the knowledge of their world than those of the age below 18.

Data Presentation And Analysis

Before getting into the actual presentation and analysis of the recorded data, it should be borne in mind that, not all the recordings are here-in transcribed. The fact is that transcriptions are not substitute for the recording but, rather a selective theory-laden rendering of certain aspects of what the tape has preserved of the original interaction. This is in line with the observation made by Heritage, J. (1984) that the transcriptions are often construed as partial presentation of the recorded data.

Following this stand, the present paper exhibits only certain selected, albeit relevant „fragment“ (in this instance argument episode) from the original recordings which are preserved on the tape. It should be noted here though, in this case, a very large portion of the recording is transcribed instead of only the selected fragment from it. This would be due to context related problems. In some recordings, context is not immediately clear with the transcription of the excerpt alone unless the reader of the transcript relates it to the larger portion of the recording. Where context is immediately clear reading the excerpt under study, only the excerpt is usually transcribed and presented. Another issue is that of translation of the original language of the data. Due to its complexity and time consuming nature, the issue of translation is here restricted to only the excerpt under analysis.

The presentation comprises of a single transcription from a selected recording on the tape. The recording is identified by time, date and place of its execution. In the same way, the transcribed portion is identified by the recording from which it is derived. Thus, from this recording there is only one selected instance of „argument talks“ transcribed, translated and analyzed.

The analysis is conducted following six separate steps. The steps are: Opening and closing remarks (2) Turn-taking organization (3) sequence organization (4) repair organization (5) organization of turn design and (6) the formulation of the exchange patterns. All these are considered on the portion under analysis. At the end of the paper, a general summary and conclusion is given. This will reflect as it were, the findings as well as the observation made from the result of the study.

PRESENTATION OF THE DATA

The following transcription is a representation of a portion of the recording made on the 6th of May, 2026. The data was recorded at 8.20pm local time with a continuous noise from a nearby electric generator on the background. The talks involved five participants in actual interaction, identified as BN, UJ, AN, MN and BR respectively. The total number of people sitting at the place of recording (Daba) is 7 including the data collector (i.e. the researcher). The topic of the conversation is politics, in which participants discuss the issue of some eminent members of the PDP party decamping to another party (APC).

EXCERPT: FROM AKALAWA MAY, 2026, SOKOTO NIGERIA

- 1 BN: Mun dade gidan „yantawaaye
- 2 Da ni da Dogo =
- 3 UJ: = Garin ga?
- 4 BN: = Garin ga ko.
- 5 (2.0)

- 6 BN: Tun karhe bakwai na safe
7 Mun ka tai (2.0) can wallah,
8 inaa ganin kaduuna zaa su na.
- 9 BN: °Shii Alhaji Husaini had – dubuu
10 biya –yyabban
- 11 UJ °°Hussaini ↑°°
12 (5.0)
- 13 UJ: Lallai su:: ina ganin su Alero
14 In sun kooma APC:::↑
15 (5.0)
- 16 AN: °°Sai an shirya[h°°=
17 BN: =Ni] wallahi inda
18 nig- gaane su Adamu Aliero
19 APC zaa suna, a kwai wani
20 yaaron Abba Alero, abookina na,
21 muna Magana dashi, shekaran jiya
22 yaa taho nan shiy-yag ga taamu,
- 23 UJ: °mmm° =
- 24 BN: = sai yacce min::↑, mu wallahi
25 Bello maa↑, inaa ganin APC mun kayi
- 26 BN: Nicce mai don Allah bari wag-ga Magana,
27 yac-ce wallahi kiilan APC mun kayi. (1.0)
28 yaa fada min Magana-n nan yaw, goobe,
29 mun k ayi waya da Dogo, =
30 =°°mmm°°
31 = mu naa Magana da Dogo, yac-ce min
32 su Aleru APC zaa su kooma.
33 (4.0)
- 34 BN: To, sai nik-kaawo wac-can magana-dda::
35 wanga da yayyi da ni sshe: ga yaw,
36 to, sai nig-game su da wan nan,
37 (2.0)
- 38 BN: To, sai gaa jarida, ni nig-gane ta
39 da kai-na gidan Yuuyu, WHAALON Yuuyu
40 nig-gane ta, ,,cce Alero zaa su kooma
41 APC (3.0). Ni*nig-ganee ta wallahi
42 gidan Yuuyu (2.0) jaridan –nan =
- 43 UJ: =Ni ko yaw wani yaa fadaa min
44 yac-ce:: yaa ga mootoocin Tafida din –
45 nan =
- 46 BN: =°°mmm°°, an rubuutaa musu APC [ko?

- 47 UJ: Anyi ra:[l, ko↑ an yi ralli↑
 48 an rubuuta musu APC =
- 49 BN: = Aahh TO↓ (0.1) to, taa tabbata
 50 kenan↓
 51 (4.0)
- 52 UJ: °°°yaayi↓°°°
 53 (5.0)
- 54 BN: AMMAH::: (1.0) na wanga zaa
 55 su yi, (0.1) na Baafaraawa da DPP =
- 56 UJ: = °mmm° =
- 57 BN: = Aii gwamma su ma zauna cikin
 58 PDP im maa kaashe su zaa°a yi,
 59 a kaashe su, sai su (1.0) waii, im
 60 maa yu – nn :: (2.0) tahoowaa
 61 zaa su yi su nuuna an gyaara
 62 matsala, sai su ci amaana-ssu (1.0)
 63 to, yaahi sauki bisa ga baa su
 64 jam „iyyat =
- 65 UJ: = °To lallai ↑° =
- 66 BN: = Naa rantche da Allah, barin
 67 AP-, koomaawa APC garee su
 68 iyaaka -bbannah↓ (0.2) Duk wanda
 69 ka Kaura murma shi kai. (SMILE)
 70 °wallahi° =
- 71 UJ: = °ko?°=
- 72 BN: =Wallahi, (1.0) su Adamu Aleiro sun
 73 kooma APC
 74 (NOISE FROM THE BACKGROUND)
 75 (4.0)
- 76 BN: Wallahi murma su kai (1.0)
 77 Yuuyu↑, in kag-ga wada ya
 78 ka murna sai kaa yi maamaaki
 79 (SMILE)
- 80 UJ: °mmm°
- 81 BN: Mitin sun k ayi ta yi (1.0) wallahi,
 82 (1.0), gida nai nig-ganee ta, cikin
 83 Whaalo nai wallaahi (2.0)
 84 Shi yas-sa kaj-ji naa fadaa ma
 85 wag-ga Magana
 86 (5.0)
- 87 UJ: Aii sun yi shirme =

- 88 BN: = ANAH [Magana::: ↑
 89 [Aii gaara suyi –
 90 zaman su nan cikin jam“iyyat.
 91 (3.0)
 92 BN: Aii kama – gGaari Maalan naa
 93 (2.0) Gaari Maala[n:::, =
 94 UJ: =[Shii Gaari Maalan
 95 Inaa zai kooma? =
 96 BN: Gaari Maalan, Aah, (1.0) suu zai bii
 97 (1.0) CPC yay-yi ↓. (1.0) Gaari Maalan
 98 aii kaa san: abinda yas-sa yan [z(·) =
 99 UJ: suu [biyu zaa“a
 100 zaa“a yi masu firaamare ke nan ko?
 101 SN: Aww↑=
 102 AN: =°° Da Gaari°°?
 103 BN: Ahh, Aww↑=
 104 UJ: = Da shi da Tafiida ba↑
 105 AN: = Ah:“ah, APC kam aii baa tada firaamare.
 106 UJ: Mii?
 107 AN: °°Ah “ah, baa ta da firaamare.
 108 UJ: Ah, in „yan taakara biyu sun ka fito
 109 AN: °Ah“a baata da firaamare.
 110 UJ: [In „yan taakara biyu sun ka fito kuuko sai
 111 [anyi firaamare
 112 MA: [Ah, in „yan taakara biyu sun ka fito sai
 113 an yii shi.
 114 (3.0)
 115 AN: °°Mmmhhh°°, ()Sulhuntaawa a kai (1.0)
 116 Irin haka ai baa“a firaamare↓°°
 117 Ai, PDP adda wannan matsala (2.0)..
 118 PDP ad-da wannan flraamare.
 119 (BACKGROUND NOISE)
 120 BR: A daina firaamaren koko mi?
 121 UJ: Eh?
 122 BN: °To haka nis-sani nii kan ↓°=
 123 UJ: Ko wace jam“iyyah akwai kaa -
 124 ida-f-firaamare, ko wace jam“iyyah
 125 sai [dai in ba“a samu:: (5.0) ba“a ssamu::
 126 BN: [sai dai in an shirya =
 127 UJ: = ko PDP, in dai an ka saamu
 128 shiri ai shikenan =

- 129 BN: = Baa dole sai an yi ba ko (2.0)
 130 don, don don wancan zaabe da
 131 an ka yi↑ (2.0) PDP, in kaa duuba
 132 du-s State level maa wasu wurairai ba
 133 suyi zaabe ba =
 134 UJ: Iyaaka zama aka yi an [ka tsatstaara =
 135 BN: = an[ka tsaara, anka]
 136 shirya[
 137 UJ: = [wanga nan, wanga nan]
 138 wan-ga nan, shi ke nan.
 139 (8.0)
 140 UJ: Lallai in sun kooma [APC [n nan::::↑
 141 BN: [Bari in taashi
 142 in aje “Chairman” (2.0) bari in kurba
 143 Lipton-ga in taashi in yi gaba.

The Analysis

1. Opening and Closing Remarks

The argument in this excerpt begins from line (92) with an opening remark from the participant BN, *Ali Kama-g Gaari Malan na:::* ' The closing of the argument is marked by another remark from the sam participant in lines (141 – 143), *'Bari in taashi in aje 'Chairman... (2.0), bari in kurba Lipton-ga... .'*

2. Turn and Turn-taking Organization

As to the feature of turn management in this episode, we can see that there are overlappings and gaps in speeches. The overlapping speeches are manifest in 93/94, 98/99, 111/112, 125/126, 134/135, 136/137, 140/141. There are gaps and some are even quite long, over 1 second: 93(2.0), 96(1.0) 97(1.0), 114(3.0), 115(1.0), 117(2.0), 129(2.0), 131(2.0), 139(8.0), 142(2.0). The gaps in 93, 96 and 97 are „intra-turn“ pauses belonging to the participant **BN** who seems to be the primary speaker in the episode. The long pause of 3 seconds in 114(3.0) is an inter-turn“ pause that comes after the participant MA (111) appears to have relinquished the floor. Next, participant AN takes his turn in 115. Other pauses in 115(1.0), and 117(2.0) belong to AN whose turn stretches from 115 – 118. Then there is a loud noise from the background in 119. At this moment an opportunity opens for BR to take the turn and his remark is short, it has come in the form of question in 120. The loud sound from the background trails for a while and this is evident in the response of UJ in 121, „Eh?“, showing that the previous remark made by BR in 120 has not been understood. There is absence of pause from line 121-128. In BN“s turn in lines 129 – 133 two „intra-turn“ pauses can be observed, 129(2.0) and 131(2.0), but the speaker continues his speech without any threat from other participants until at the end when his speech seems to latch with the supporting remark of UJ at 129/130. After that there appears to be a normal one-at-a time resumption of turn management without any apparent instances of gaps. A longish pause of 8 seconds seems to occur in line 139, where all speakers remain silent in line 140 perhaps with the intent of re-cycling the conversation, a turn which is interruption by BN (141 – 143) “[*Bari in taashi in aje 'Chairman' ...*] (Let me take the Chairman home). This marks the closing of the episode.

Turn-takings and pauses in conversational interaction such as this are two related phenomena for turn organizational construction. The pauses provide break markers where possible turn relevant places (TRPS) occur. These features and these facts are seen as a continuous achievement of the parties to the conversation, which they accomplish on a turn-by-turn basis and a means by which they manage and run smoothly the conversation traffic.

3. Sequence Organization

Sequence organization is one of the core ideas in conversation analysis (CA). It means that in interactional talks, utterances are sequentially arranged. This idea of sequence corresponds to our common experience that „one thing can lead to another“.

In conversation, it implies that any utterance in interaction is considered to have been produced for the place in the progression of the talk, that is, the place or the slot it fits in, just after the preceding one, while at the same time it creates a context for its own next utterance e.g. Question/Answer, Greeting/response etc. The major instrument for the analysis of sequence organization in conversation is the concept of adjacency pair (AP).

A sequence however, is restricted to a pair in this, just two pair-parts. Starting from the core-sequence as our point of departure, additional sequences can be seen as expanding it in various ways. But it is the relationship between the two pair-parts of utterance that is „normative. After a pair, the next pair-part (i.e. utterance) is heard as the relevant response to the first as a fitting second pair part. When such second pair-part is not possible or is absent or when there is no response to the first pair-part, or when it occurs but does not fit into the slot it occupied, that is an accountable matter, a noticeable absence.

Beside the obligatory first and second pair-parts there are certain non-nominative, non-obligatory parts or expansions of various kinds. Basically, in adjacency pair structure, the second pair-part is expected in the immediate next position. In certain cases however, where this does not occur and or, the non-occurrence is not noticeable another expansion of the sequence may take place. An example is when a first speaker asks question and the next speaker instead of giving an answer replies with a question, there is a tendency that the first speaker answers the second question before the second speaker answers the first. This will make the sequence to appear as Q1, Q2, A2, A1.

Some adjacency pair formatted utterances function as a preparation for a next pair and such utterances can be of different types as pre-sequences: pre-invitations, pre-requests, pre-announcements etc. Others may lead to temporary lifting of the ordinary turn-taking system, a situation whereby one party gets the right to produce a multi-turn unit like in a story telling or a joke and that party in talk automatically becomes recipients.

Another kind of expansion is post expansion. This occurs sometimes as a third-position acknowledgement or assessment or repairs or a re-work of the core-sequence. Some endless series of sequences can be observed in arguments also as counter-arguments, reproaches, defences and the like.

In the current Analysis, this fragment (92-143) is a continuation of a long conversation on the issue of certain members of a political party decamping to another party. Most of the discussion on the topic has been advanced in the previous sequence (See the main body of transcription in 111(1)).

I arrived at the Daba“ at the time before the actual talks began. Participant BN begins by citing the case of one „Gaari Maalan“ 92 – 93 in the middle of the conversation. This sequence (92-93) is a pre-sequence which immediately provoked another sequence uttered by UJ in 94 in the form of question. As can be seen, there are a number of pauses in the subsequent sequence to 94 by the next participant BN (96-98). This is interrupted by another question by the participant UJ in lines 99-100;

„*suu biyu zaa'a yi musu 'primary' ke nan ko*“? A fitting sequence follows immediately after, with a prompt answer „*Aww*“ (yes!) by BN in line 101. There is an extension of the second pair-part sequence 101 in 102 by participant AN demanding the elaboration of the answer given ^{oo}*Da Gaari?*^{oo} (^{oo}with Gaari?^{oo}) which is followed immediately by another stressed answer in 103 similar to the first. The next sequence in line 104 is belonged to UJ and it functions as an expansion and clarification of the immediate preceding sequence. A fresh sequence is produced by AN in 105 serving as core sequence to the next sequence in 106 by UJ in the form of question „*mi?* (but why?).

An argument becomes evident in the subsequent utterance by AN in line 106 where he emphasizes his stand in line 105 „*Ah:ah APC kam aii baa tada firaamare*“ (No, no APC has no primaries). Another sequence follows as a counter-argument by UJ (108) and in 109 we see another statement by AN similar to the one in 105, which is again-counter argued now, by UJ in 110 and MA in (112-113).

After a longish pause of 3 seconds (114), AN resumes the floor in 115-118 and his statement is again counter argued by the participant BR in line 120 amidst background noise. The other subsequent sequences all follow as defences against the claim of AN that there is no primary election for the APC

party. The argument trails on one-sequence-after-the-other and there is a longish pause of 8 seconds after which the talks resume in 139.

There is one noticeable feature here. In line 140, UJ begins a sequence of the current topic of discussion after the long silence but, in the subsequent sequence we see a deviation by participant BN in 141. The remark made here (141) does not fit in the slot as a legitimate second pair-part to the first. This deviation marks the closing of the argument episode.

4. Repair Organization

In conversation, interactants often encounter various kinds of troubles in the interaction progress. Problems such as those of mishearing or misunderstanding are very often met with and most likely, though not always the case, repairs are initiated by complaints like the English remark, „pardon“, I can’t hear you or what?“ etc. Once such repair is initiated, a bar is set that result into a postponement of a projected next action. Studies have shown that a repair can be self-initiated or other initiated and it can be done or affected by the original speaker, in which case it is self-repair“ or by others which is „other repair“. Thus a speaker can cut off the current utterance they have made to re-start it, thereby correcting an obvious mistake or using a different expression. On the other hand, a speaker may use a transition relevant place (TRP) just after the utterance is completed to initiate a self repair. Still, a turn’s recipient may react to an utterance made by other speaker in some way to demonstrate some kind of misunderstanding. Also, another speaker can give an appropriate utterance to repair some mistake made by a current speaker. Where an immediate repair is supposed to occur in the next and it does not, this is considered an event of not-doing-repair.

There is only one obvious aspect of repair in this argument episode. This can be observed in line 121. It is initiated by UJ as a result of misunderstanding of BR remarks in 119. This is perhaps due to the background noise indicated in line 118. This repair however is not done by any of the participants in the interaction. One possible reason for „not-doing-repair“ in this case could be due to the subsequent remark of BN in 122. The remark is the confirmation of 121 to indicate that the action is captured by him and therefore needs not to be re-done.

Let me say at this point that repair cases though frequently occurring in conversation, do not make a regular part of interaction (see Ten Have, 2001). Repair is typically occasioned by problems of understanding. Therefore, the occurrence of one instance of repair in this episode signifies that the interaction is well understood by the participants and that it is successful.

A typical case of repair can be observed in the main body of the transcription on page 72 lines 57 – 64. This portion of the transcription does not fall within the argument excerpt under present analysis. However, it is considered here as a good instance of repair for this analysis.

57 BN: -Aii gwamma su maa zauna cikin
58 PDP im maa kaashe su zaa‘‘ayi,
59 a kaashe su sai su (1.0) waii-im
60 maa yu – nn:: (2.0) tahoowaa
61 zaa su yi su nuuna an gyaara
62 matsala, sai su ci amaana-ssu (1.0)
63 to, yaahi sauki bisa ga baa su
64 jam „iyyat =

Here, BN initiates a repair from line 57 to a 1 second pause in line 59. After the pause he then starts to do the repair by first making the statement „waii‘ (oh no!) in the same line, thus highlighting the occurrence of a repair in his previous utterance, before his subsequent struggle in the proceeding lines (60 – 64) to re-work his statement. This is one of the typical examples of self-initiated and self-done repair by Sakkwatanci speakers. It is characterized by the use of some familiar paralinguistic vocalizations such as „waii‘ to signify that a current statement is cut off and is to be corrected or re-started.

5. The Organization of Turn Design

This has to do with preference organization in talks. Since it has no collaborate structured approach in the CA as have the three organizational issues just considered, the work has chosen here to omit it and proceed to the structure-analysis formulation of the exchange pattern as they may be revealed in the excerpt.

6. Formulation of Exchange Pattern

It is hinted in the introduction section of this paper, any piece of conversation whether formal or informal such as the one under study is not just a bunch of strings of words or language forms to which one can allot individual functions, but a structured unit with patterns of some kind. However, due to the multi-party nature of informal conversation like this one and the non-restricted freedom of participants in turn-taking, finding rigid patterns is hard but not unlikely.

There are some regular recurring patterns with varying shapes and contents observed here, which appear in the form of question/response and comment/follow-up exchanges. This pattern recurs throughout the argument. Examples of these can be seen in:

Lines 99-100/101	=	Question/response
102/103	=	Question/response
104/105	=	Comment/follow-up
106/107	=	Question/response

Most of the moves constituting units exchanges in this regard function as argument and counter-argument.

iv. Conclusion

Recording of talks has been extremely difficult for this work. It appears quite difficult to make participants in conversation to behave normally before certain strange persons. This has made recording exercise almost impossible in certain places. Even where the participants in talks appear familiar and friendly, some disturbing obstacles frequently occur. There have been from time to time physical and operational noises.

Another aspect of difficulty encountered in the course of this work is one of transcribing the recorded data. In CA transcribing talks is tedious and cumbersome. Repeated playing and replaying of recordings is required in order to capture the salient features of the recorded talks. This process has been time consuming and often frustrating. A lot of the tapes have been damaged and disposed off in the process. Due to resulting constraints imposed by these problems and the limit of the work, the data has been narrowly selected.

As can be seen in the selected piece of argument talks, the organization progression is based on five steps: turn-taking organization, sequence organization, repair organization turn design and the formulation of exchange patterns. All these steps have been discussed in relation to the piece under study and this constitutes the general analysis of the whole argument episode.

The turns appear to run smoothly to the end of the argument with the participants **BN** seeming to be the primary speaker of the conversation. From line 92 where the argument episode is said to begin to line 143 which marks its closing, there is a total of 27 turns belonging to various participants. Of this number, a total of 8 separate turns are owned by **BN** and the remaining 19 turns belong to the other participants: **UJ**, **AN**, **MA** and **BR**. The argument begins with **BN** giving an example of someone decamping form their political party to another. The central issue of the argument is whether there will be a primary election between the two contestants within the party. Most of the pauses are „within-turn-pauses“ (intra turns) and there are a number of overlapping speeches and questions which seem to slow the traffic flow of the talks. There are latches of talks among adjacent turns and this feature is frequent, showing certain agreement or alignment of points between adjacent speakers. Certain latches also occur between turns to show disagreement.

There are very few cases of repair in the episode. Only one marked case of repair has been observed and its resultant effect is a „not-doing-repair.“ The reason of not doing repair initiated by (121) could be due to the quick remark in 122 made by BN. *To haka nis-sani nii kan*’. (This is indeed what I personally know).

In an informal free conversational situation such as this one, there can be discerned no rigid patterns as is with the case of formal setting (e.g pupil-teacher talks , doctor-patient etc.) this may be due to non-censorship nature of talks in this kind of settings. There is however some kind of pattern observed even though it is a multiparty-non-censorship form of interaction. Some regular recurring patterns of questions/response and comment/follow-up have however been observed.

This research work is considered an attempt to study a piece of recording of argument talks in Hausa. In terms of turn-taking, adjacency, repair and turn design organization. The following observation on the analysis are made:

First, the study shows that talk in casual conversation are excessively free with individual speakers ready at any moment to take up a turn relevant position (TRP) opportunity. The study reveals that participants compete freely for turns in argument with no current speaker having the mandate to appoint the next speaker. Secondly, conversational talks particularly those in argument are typically noisy, joky and sometimes reproachful. Third, arguments are often not pre-arranged they occur in the course of normal conversation with topics emerging abruptly either initiated by statement or by asking questions. Fourth, participants in argument often take sides freely and they show this through multiple comments, signifying supports or disagreement where agreement occurs among speakers this is indicated occasionally by latches in speeches or overlaps. This is not to say that latching and overlapping of speeches are used as instruments of consensus in argument. Such devices are in certain instances used to register counter-arguments.

Finally, adjacency pairing progresses normally in arguments with pairs matching to enhance the traffic flow. Pre-sequences are used to mark the beginning of the arguments in the form of statements or questions. Pairs are also expanded in various ways either as pre or post sequences. In many occasions the use of this mechanisms is seen as instrumental in launching a defense or supporting a point.

Key to Reading the Transcriptions

The transcript symbols used in this work for the transcription are given below. They are means to explain the major conventions for rendering details of the vocal production of utterances in talk-in-interaction as used in most current CA publications. Most of them have been developed by Gail Jefferson and are now used with minor individual variations. They are provided here in order to serve a key to reading the transcriptions made in this paper.

Sequencing

- [A single left bracket indicates the point of overlap onset.
-] A single right bracket indicates the point at which an utterance or utterance-part terminates vis-à-vis another
- = Equal signs, one at the end of one line and one at the beginning of a next, indicate no „gap“ between the two lines. This is often called „latching“

Timed Intervals

- (0.0) Numbers in parentheses indicate lapsed time in silence by tenth of seconds, so (5.1) is a pause of 5 seconds and one-tenth of a second.
- (.) A dot in parenthese indicates a tiny „gap“ within or between utterances.

Characteristics of Speech Production

Word, Underscoring indicates some form of „stress“ via pitch and/or amplitude; an alternative method is to print the stressed part in Bold Capital Letters.

- :: Colons indicate prolongations of the immediately prior sound while multiple colons indicates a more prolonged sound.
- A dash indicate a cut-off, and where it occurs at last at the end of a line it indicates a connection of word parts from one line to the next.
- ?? Punctuation marks are used to indicate characteristics of speech production, especially intonation, they are not referring to grammatical units, an alternative is an italicized question mark.
- . A period indicates a stopping fall in tone.
- , A comma indicates a continuing intonation, like double aa, uu, ee Double vowel letters indicate a normal double vowel lengthening.
- ↑↓ Arrows indicate marked shifts into higher or lower pitch in the utterance part immediately

following the arrow

- Degree designs, utterances or utterance parts bracketed by degree designs are relatively quieter than the surrounding talks

[From Ten Have, 2007 with slight modifications]

REFERENCES

- Austin, J.L. (1962) How to do things with words. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- Brown, G. and Yule, G. (1983) Discourse Analysis, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
- Chomsky, N. (1957) Syntactic Structures, Mouton: The Hague
- Chomsky, N. (1975) Syntactic structures. The Hague: Mouton.
- Garfinkel, H. (1967) Studies in Ethnomethodology. Eaglewood Cliffs, N.J Prentice Hall
- Have, P. Ten (2007) Doing Conversation Analysis: A practical Guide London: Sage
- Heath, C. and P. Luff (1993) „The delivery and reception of diagnosis in the general practice consultation“. In: P. Drew, J. Heritage (eds), Talk at work, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Heritage, J. (1984) A change of state token and aspects of its sequential placement“. In (ed.) Atkinson, J. and Heritage, Structures of Social Action: Studies in Conversation Analysis, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. Pp. 299-345
- Lyons, J. (1981) Semantics, 2 vols. Cambridge: C.U.P Malinowski (1975).
- Mary, J.L. (1993) Pragmatics: Introduction, Oxford Blackwell Pub. Ltd
- McCarthy, N. (1991) Discourse Analysis for Language Teachers, Cambridge
- McCarthy, N. (2001) Issues in Applied Linguistics Oxford University Press
- Newman, P. (2000) The Hausa Language: An Encyclopedic Reference Grammar. New Haven: Yale University Press.
- Partridge. B. (2007) Discourse Analysis, New York: New York Continuum Press
- Sacks, H. (1974) On the Analyzability of stories by children, In: Turner, R. (ed.) Ethnomethodology, Middles Penguin Press.
- Sacks, H. (1995) Lectures on conversation Vol,1-11 (Gail Jefferson (ed.) Oxford, Blackwell)
- Sacks, H. (2004) „An initial characterization of the organization of speaker-turn-talking in conversation“. In G.H. Lerner (ed.) Conversation Analysis: Studies from the first generation, Amsterdam/Philadelphia, John Benjamins: 35-42
- Sacks, H., Schegloff, E.A. & Jefferson, G. (1974) A Simplest systematics for the organization of turn-taking for conversation. Language, 50(4), 696-735.
- Sinclair, J. McH and Coulthard, R.M 91975) Towards an Analysis of Discourse „The English used by Teachers and Pupils, Oxford University Press.
- Sinclair, J.M and H.M. Coulthard (1975) Towards and Analysis of Discourse, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.